

A Deep Learning Approach for Classification of Healthy and Diseased Leaf Images using ResNet152

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Abstract: India is mainly an agro based country where good quality production of crops plays a very important role but frequent attack of pathogens leads to severe crop damage thus, decreasing their yield which poses a major threat to the food security. This, in turn affects the economy of our country very much and the farmers suffers great loss. Thus, proper monitoring of the crops on regular basis is very important to take proper actions on time and save the crops from further damage. Artificial Intelligence plays a crucial role in addressing several concerns in agriculture, thus it is important that the farmers should be provided with AI based technologies to boost up crop production. In this paper we propose a transfer learning based approach for classification of healthy and diseased bean leaf plants using ResNet152 pre-trained model. The performance metrics of the model was studied by evaluating the four important parameters: classification accuracy, precision, recall and f1-score. Experimental result proved that ResNet152 performs better with a higher accuracy (0.89) and f1-score (0.88) than the other pre-trained models. Further a training accuracy of 97% was achieved in just 30 epochs of the ResNet152 model. A comparison table of the performance parameters of the different pre-trained models is also summarized at the end of the paper.

Keywords: Agriculture, Artificial Intelligence, Pre-trained Models, Residual Network, Transfer Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

India has a worldwide reputation in good quality agriculture production. More than half of the population in India is involved in cultivation of different varieties of fruits, vegetables, crops etc. As of 2011, India had a large and diverse agricultural sector, accounting, on average, for about 16% of GDP and 10% of export earnings [1]. India's arable land area of 159.7 million hectares (394.6 million acres) is the second largest in the world, after the United States [2]. Thus, ensuring proper quality of crops and vegetables production is of utmost important for India's economy. But, vegetation, in tropical areas is always prone to pathogen attacks leading to many diseases in plants, which decrease the overall crop production. In general, a plant becomes diseased when it is continuously disturbed by some causal agent that results in an abnormal physiological process that disrupts the plant's normal structure, growth, function, or other activities [3]. Organisms like bacteria, virus, fungus or any other infectious agents can severe damage to the crops leading poor yield. Consuming such diseased plants may lead to serious health problems. In addition, plant disease can devastate natural ecosystems and cause environmental problems by habitat loss and poor land management [4].

And in a country like India, where majority of the people's only source of income is farming, poor cultivation yield can cause catastrophic loss in their lives. Thus, it is very important that the farmers should be well equipped with the latest AI based technologies to keep on monitoring the health of the plants on a regular basis, so that proper action can be taken on the right time. Artificial intelligence have played major role in addressing problems in major sectors such as health, self driving cars, image classification etc. and thus, AI is a rising revolution in agriculture sector too. AI can help the farmers to cope up with several challenges in agriculture like monitoring plant diseases, weed detection, monitoring of pest and pathogens, harvesting etc. Researchers have explored the Traditional Machine Learning models in plant disease detection and found that these models a only perform well with a minimal amount of data and its efficiency decreases as the amount of data increases. Further, the manual process of feature extraction serves as a limitation of these techniques. Thus, researchers began to turn their attention in deep learning models, which are the state of art technology that has been recently explored as an alternative to machine learning models.

This paper utilizes the new concept of "**Transfer Learning**" using PTMs, instead of Traditional Machine Learning to detect the diseased and the healthy leaves. This is entirely a new concept that have been recently being in used various image classification task. Through this paper we throw some insight into how the concept of transfer learning using PTMs can be utilized in classification of healthy and diseased bean leaves. Transfer learning is a most powerful tool to achieve impressive state-of-the-art results. Unlike in traditional machine learning, the **learning process** in transfer learning is much faster, more accurate and need less training data. Transfer learning focuses on storing knowledge from previously existing models and then using the knowledge to solve a new problem completely. Further, there is no need to manually extract the features from the image as the network learns to extract the features while training. Also, transfer learning offers a higher learning rate during training since the problem has already being trained for a similar task.

Thus, owing to the different benefits of transfer learning, we have decided to utilize this new concept in detection of diseased and healthy bean leaves. There are two approaches of deep learning: one is developing the whole model from scratch and the other to use a pre-trained model (also known as transfer learning). The former is time consuming, so we have decided to use pre-trained models for our purpose.

In this paper, we have proposed a method for classification of healthy and diseased bean leaves based on "transfer learning" with the help of pre trained model ResNet152. This model is trained on ImageNet, which is a dataset of over 15 million labeled high

resolution images with around 22,000 categories. Transfer learning is basically the concept where the network gains knowledge from a previous problem and tries to solve a completely new problem based on its acquired knowledge [5]. ResNet152 is a classical neural network with 152 layers which utilizes a technique known as “residual mapping”. Fig 1 shows the architecture of a residual network.

Figure1: Architecture of a residual network [6].

The main benefit of transfer learning is the use of PTMs which are previously trained on huge dataset. Also, transfer learning using PTMs proves to be more beneficial in comparison to building a network from scratch.

The organization of the paper is as follows: the first section of the paper gives the introduction about the importance of agriculture in our Indian economy, stating the factors that threaten food security. This section also explains how AI based technology can help the farmers keep a track on the health of the plants. The second section describes the various works supported in literature similar of this kind. The third section gives the details about the materials and methods used in our research followed by the fourth section which is dedicated to the results obtained from our proposed method. Finally, the fifth section concludes the paper with highlighting the importance of our method.

II. RELATED WORKS

In recent time transfer learning has gained a lot of importance by the researchers in image classification, starting from medical image classification to scene understanding. Various researchers from the globe have proposed different methods of plant disease detection in several ways. Malusi et.al., have developed a computational procedure for recognition and classification of maize leaves diseases out of healthy leaves using Convolutional Neural Networks. The developed model was able to recognize three different types of maize diseases from healthy leaves. The authors claimed to obtain an accuracy of 92.85% [7]. Durmus et.al., have developed a tomato leaves disease detection method using deep learning models AlexNet and SqueezeNet. The training and validation was done on Nvidia jetson TX1. The authors claimed that their proposed system can successfully detect the disease class from the healthy class [8]. Picon et.al., have developed a deep convolution neural network model for crop disease identification which proved to be very successful for different classification task. The authors performed early identification of wheat diseases and claimed to obtain fruitful results [9]. Cheng et.al., have developed a tea leaf disease detection method using LeafNet Algorithm. The authors found that the LeafNet algorithm was superior in disease identification task compared to other MLP algorithms [10]. Wang et.al., have developed a deep learning model to identify wheat disease plants from healthy plants. The authors developed a 2D-CNN-BidGRU for identification and claimed to obtain an accuracy of 74% [11]. Sun et.al. has developed a cucumber leaf disease detection method using DCNN (Deep Convolution Neural Network) and compared their results with other existing ML algorithms. The authors found their proposed system more efficient than other traditional ML algorithms [12]. Canals et.al has developed a deep learning approach method for identifying vine diseases in grapevines. Their proposed method utilizes CNN and colour information to detect disease systems in the vineyards. The authors claimed to obtain fruitful results [13]. Jones et.al., has developed a deep learning model for plant disease identification using hyperspectral data. The authors developed a 3D CNN model for soyabean disease identification. Their model has a classification accuracy of 95.73% [14].

III. METHODOLOGY

The dataset used here is the “Beans” dataset, which is publicly available in the tensorflow hub. The dataset consist of images of diseased bean leaf plants classified into two categories namely: angular leaf spot and bean rust, along with healthy leaves. The test and train and validation dataset contains 128, 1034 and 133 images respectively. Fig 2 shows some of the leaves from our dataset.

Figure 2: Dataset of the bean leaf [15].

ResNet152 is a three layer deep network consisting of 152 layers. The main concept behind ResNet model is using of “skipped connections”, where the input layer is directly connected to the output layer after skipping a few connections. One of the major advantages of using ResNet is that the training error, decreases as the layers increases, whereas in comparison with other plain networks the training error at first decreases with increase in number of layers but then gradually increases [16]. ResNet has been applied recently to many computer vision and image processing task successfully. Fig3, shows the architecture of the ResNet, with residual units, size of the filter and output of each convolution layer.

Figure 3: Architecture of ResNet152 [17].

ResNet152 has over 23 million trainable parameters and currently, gaining popularity in many image classification task.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The bean dataset was downloaded from Tensorflow datasets which is publicly available. ResNet152 pre-trained model was used and fine tuning was performed on the last layer. The training and validation datasets consist of 1034 and 133 images respectively and our testing dataset consist of 128 images. We have used Keras for constructing our deep learning model. Keras is a powerful and easy to use free open source Python library for developing and evaluating deep learning models [18]. We have created a kera sequential layer, with dropout rate as 30% and then added a final dense layer to it with three classes and have used ‘softmax’ activation. While compiling the model we have used ‘Adam Optimizer’, with Categorical Crossentropy as the loss function. Fig 4 shows the training accuracy of the model and Fig 5 shows the model loss.

Figure 5: Model Loss

We obtained a training accuracy of 97.2% in just 30 epochs with a minimal loss. The four most important performance metrics: classification accuracy, precision, recall and f1-score have been calculated from the confusion matrix to study the efficient of the ResNet152 model. Table1 shows the performance metrics obtained from ResNet152 as well as other pre-trained models.

Figure6: Confusion Matrix for ResNet152

Figure7: Confusion Matrix for MobileNetV2

Figure8: Confusion Matrix for InceptionV3

Figure9: Confusion Matrix for VGG16

Model	Classification Accuracy	Precision	Recall	f1- score
ResNet152	0.89	0.88	0.88	0.88
MobileNetV2	0.87	0.86	0.86	0.87
InceptionV3	0.86	0.87	0.91	0.85
VGG16	0.80	0.81	0.80	0.80

Table1: Comparison of the performance metrics of ResNet152 with other pre-trained models.

From the above table we can observe that the classification accuracy of ResNet152 is higher than the other models and thus, we can conclude that ResNet152 can be considered as a suitable model for real-time plant disease classification.

V. CONCLUSION

Early detection of plant disease is very important to avoid crop production loss. And, in a country like India where generally more than half of the population is engaged in agriculture, high yield of production of crops is required to feed the country’s large population. But, due to pathogenic attacks and several other environmental reasons, crops are sometimes severely damaged due to which the farmers have to suffer huge loss decreasing the crop production. Thus, it is important that the farmers keep monitoring the health of the plants on a regular basis to check any early sign of diseases. Artificial Intelligence is a rising revolution in agriculture and is helping the farmers in addressing the serious concerns in agriculture efficiently. In this paper, we have proposed a method for classification of diseased bean leaves and healthy bean leaves using transfer learning. We have used keras and tensorflow platform to construct our model. Keras is an open source software library that provides interface for developing deep learning models. We obtained a training accuracy of 97.2% with just 30 epochs using the ResNet152 model and also obtained a higher classification accuracy and f1-score in comparison with other PTMs. Thus, we can conclude that ResNet152 can be considered as an efficient deep learning model for automatic real-time classification of plant diseases.

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